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Report on data made available for research by governmental authorities

Availability of Government Data for Research Purposes

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Executive summary

This report examines how governmental data can be made more accessible and usable for research in Earth System Science (ESS) by applying the FAIR principles — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. Using High-Value Datasets (HVD) defined under Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/138 (DVO-HVD) as a pilot case, it analyses workflows, standards, and infrastructures that support discoverability and reporting.

HVD—such as national-scale climate, hydrology, and land-use datasets—must be published as Open Data, tagged in metadata, and reported at the Member State level. Their stringent requirements expose gaps in metadata quality, harvesting consistency, and cataloguing, making them ideal for testing improvements.

The report focuses on three key questions: how agencies can improve the way, they publish datasets; how ESS scientists can effectively find and access them; and what is needed for a sustainable, end-to-end data pipeline. It reviews the legal context (PSI Directive, DVO-HVD, DNG, GeoZG) and infrastructures including GDI-DE, GovData, umwelt.info, and NFDI4Earth (OneStop4All/KnowledgeHub). Findings highlight the need for harmonised metadata, semantic search, stronger feedback channels, and richer documentation.

Without claiming to propose complete technical solutions, the report provides a roadmap for strengthening data infrastructures to serve both governmental agencies and the scientific community. It shows how HVD can act as a catalyst for broader, FAIR-aligned improvements.

Call for review

This document is intended to be updated regularly. We invite you to actively contribute by providing feedback, particularly on missing data or information relevant to researchers in the OneStop4All portal of NFDI4Earth. Your input will help improve this report and ensure it meets the needs of the research community. Please send your comments to the NFDI4Earth [User Support Network contact form](#): <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>.

Abbreviations

API: Application Programming Interface BGR: Bundesanstalt für Geologie und Rohstoffe
BSH: Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie BKG: Bundesamt für Kartographie und
Geodäsie BDSG: Bundesdatenschutzgesetz / Federal Data Protection Act CSW: Catalogue
Service for the Web DCAT: Data Catalog Vocabulary DCAT-AP: Data Catalog Vocabulary
Application Profile DCAT-AP.de: deutsche Adaption des Data Catalog Vocabulary Application
Profils (= gemeinsames deutsche Metadatenmodell zum Austausch von offenen Verwaltungsdaten)
Destatis: Statistisches Bundesamt DNG: Datennutzungsgesetz / Data Use Act DSGVO:
Datenschutzgrundverordnung -> GDPR DVO-HVD: Durchführungsverordnung High-Value
Datasets DWD: Deutscher Wetterdienst ESS: Earth System Science EU: European Union EU-
HVD: European High-Value Dataset Act FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GDI-DE: Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland / German Spatial Data Infrastructure GDPR:
General Data Protection Regulation GeoZG: Geodatenzugangsgesetz / Geodata Access Act
gov-agencies: governmental agencies gov-data: governmental data HVD: High-Value Datasets
INSPIRE: Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community ISO: International
Organization for Standardization IWG: Informationsweiterverwendungsgesetz JSON: JavaScript
Object Notation (Datei- und Datenaustauschformat) JSON-LD: JavaScript Object Notation for
Linked Data Landes-GDI: Landesgeodateninfrastrukturgesetze / spatial data infrastructure and
geospatial regulations LDSG: Landesdatenschutzgesetze / State Data Protection Acts NFDI:
Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur / National Research Data Infrastructure NGO: Non-
Governmental Organization OCG: Open Geospatial Consortium OpenNRW: Open Government
in Nordrhein-Westfalen RDF: Resource Description Framework Turtle: Terse RDF Triple
Language (Syntax und Datenformat für RDF) UBA: Umweltbundesamt W3C: World Wide Web
Consortium WFS: Web Feature Service

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1 Introduction

This report, titled “**Report on Data Made Available for Research by Governmental Authorities,**” aims to improve access to governmental data (gov-data) in alignment with the FAIR principles¹ — Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. It is targeted at scientists and data-providing authorities in the field of Earth System Science (ESS) and outlines a process-oriented approach to enhance the discoverability and usability of gov-data.

To support this goal, we focus on High-Value Datasets (HVD), using a defined and delimitable dataset as a practical entry point. HVD represent standardised, high-quality inputs (e.g., climate, hydrology, land use data) that underpin Earth system models and analyses; improving their discoverability directly benefits the ESS community. Under Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/138 (“DVO-HVD”)², HVD are public-sector geospatial datasets that:

- Are listed in the Annex to the DVO-HVD (six thematic categories):
 - Geospatial
 - Earth observation and environment
 - Meteorological
 - Statistics
 - Mobility
 - Company and business registers
- Are provided in machine-readable form at all generalization levels down to 1:5 000, and
- Collectively cover the entire territory of an EU Member State.

In Germany, meteorological HVD (e.g., station observations, validated climate series) are provided by the Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD), while other authorities may contribute additional datasets.

HVD must be published as **Open Data**, marked in metadata, and included in national reporting. Their demanding scope exposes shortcomings in harvesting, metadata quality, and cataloguing—making them ideal pilots for pipeline improvement.

The report addresses three guiding questions:

- How can governmental agencies make their datasets discoverable for the scientific community?

¹ Wilkinson, M. D., et al. (2016). The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific Data*, 3, Article number: 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

² <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023R0138>

- How can ESS scientists effectively locate and access these datasets?
- What steps are needed for a sustainable, end-to-end data pipeline?

In examining these questions, the report references established standards and frameworks. Relevant metadata frameworks include:

- **INSPIRE**³ – ISO 191*-based XML metadata for geospatial data, implemented in Germany by GDI-DE.
- **G8 Open Data Charter**⁴ – DCAT AP (JSON) metadata, implemented nationwide by GovData.
- **EU-HVD**⁵ – DCAT AP-based publication of HVD, with GDI-DE supplying records and GovData providing metadata.

To enable comprehensive data discovery, the report also considers existing infrastructures such as the **Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland (GDI-DE)**⁶, **GovData**⁷—the German national data portal—and **UBA umwelt.info**⁸. All three platforms already apply DCAT-based metadata and represent key components in the evolving HVD ecosystem. Furthermore, the report incorporates perspectives from the **NFDI4Earth**⁹ initiative, particularly its **KnowledgeHub**¹⁰ and the **OneStop4All portal**¹¹, which aim to streamline metadata aggregation and improve data discoverability.

However, simply listing datasets in catalogs is insufficient; effective discovery requires both metadata and datasets to be jointly accessible and contextually relevant. The report therefore considers semantic filters and other enhancements informed by EU HVD guidelines to enable structured, interoperable searches.

Rather than prescribing fully developed technical solutions, the report proposes a pathway toward more robust, FAIR-aligned data infrastructures for ESS, identifying requirements, open issues, and promising strategies for sustained improvement.

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/2019-06-26>

⁴ <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/open-data-charter/g8-open-data-charter-and-technical-annex>

⁵ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32023R0138>

⁶ <https://www.gdi-de.org>

⁷ <https://www.govdata.de>

⁸ <https://umwelt.info>

⁹ <https://www.nfdi4earth.de>

¹⁰ <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de>

¹¹ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de>

2 Legal and Infrastructural Foundations for Governmental and HVD Metadata

2.1 Legal framework for governmental data

In June 2024, the EU High-Value Dataset (HVD) Implementing Regulation entered into force. This regulation (EU) 2023/138¹² defines a list of categories of high-value datasets that must be made available for free re-use by governmental authorities across all EU member states. As stated in the regulation, its goal is “to ensure that public data of highest socio-economic potential are made available for re-use with minimal legal and technical restrictions and free of charge.”¹³

In Germany, the INSPIRE Directive is primarily implemented through the Geodata Access Act (GeoZG¹⁴), which establishes national regulations for geospatial interoperability and access. At state level, complementary spatial data infrastructure and geospatial regulations (Landes-GDI) refine responsibilities and technical specifications, ensuring INSPIRE standards are operationalised across state administrations.

Already in 2007, the EU launched the INSPIRE initiative to support “the purposes of Community environmental policies and policies or activities which may have an impact on the environment”¹⁵ This initiative aimed to build a common EU-wide infrastructure for geospatial data, setting essential standards for data interoperability and accessibility. INSPIRE laid the groundwork for harmonizing environmental and geospatial data across Europe.

Over time, research and practical experience demonstrated that public sector data serves citizens, researchers, and businesses best when it is openly accessible. This realisation led to the EU's Open Data Initiative and the adoption of the PSI Directive (EU) 2019/1024¹⁶, which sought to make public sector information more widely usable by science and the economy. However, to sharpen the focus on datasets with the highest potential societal benefits, the HVD regulation was introduced.

The HVD regulation builds on the principles of the PSI Directive (EU) 2019/1024, specifying categories like geospatial, meteorological, and environmental data as high-value datasets. These datasets are seen as key drivers for innovation, economic growth, and societal progress. They may be expanded in future to reflect scientific and technological progress. In Germany, the regulation was first implemented through updates to the Informationsweiterverwendungsgesetz

¹² https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/138/oj/eng

¹³ Chapter (2): https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/138/oj/eng

¹⁴ <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/geozg>

¹⁵ Article 1: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32007L0002&qid=1752146988381>

¹⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/1024/oj?eliuri=eli%3Adir%3A2019%3A1024%3Aoj&locale=en>

(IWG)¹⁷ which adopted the earlier EU directive 2003/98/EG¹⁸. When this directive became substituted by 2019/1024 the IWG became an update and was replaced by the new *Datennutzungsgesetz* (DNG)¹⁹ in 2021, ensuring compliance with EU requirements. The DNG expanded data categories, emphasized FAIR principles, and reduced restrictions. The development reflects growing awareness of data's socio-economic value and the need for harmonized, accessible, and innovation-driven data policies in the digital age.

In parallel with the regulations on open data and high-value datasets, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR/DSGVO²⁰) is implemented in Germany through the Federal Data Protection Act (BDSG), which is supplemented by State Data Protection Acts (LDSG). Similarly, state-level Freedom of Information and Open Data laws implement and extend the obligations and reuse measures introduced by the *Datennutzungsgesetz* (DNG) for subnational public bodies.

The GDI-DE plays a central role in coordinating the provision and accessibility of these datasets. The structured provision pathway outlined in the regulatory framework involves federal, state and local authorities consolidating and standardising data sets in accordance with their obligations under the BDSG/LDSG (data protection), GeoZG/Landes-GDI (geodata) and DNG (open data), before forwarding them to the GDI-DE. This multi-layered compliance and technical consolidation enable the scientific community at large to reuse the data.

Looking ahead, the EU plans to expand the list of high-value datasets and further improve interoperability standards. In Germany, efforts will likely focus on increasing the usability of these datasets for research and industry while integrating them with emerging technologies like artificial intelligence. Strengthening collaborations between public authorities, academia, and private enterprises is expected to maximize the societal and economic benefits of open data.

Future expansions to the list of high-value datasets will likely require coordinated adjustments to federal (DNG, GeoZG and BDSG) and state (Landes-GDI and LDSG) frameworks. This will ensure consistent interpretations for operational agencies, enabling datasets to reach infrastructures such as GDI-DE with both legal conformity and technical interoperability.

NFDI4Earth is committed to improving the availability, accessibility, findability, and quality of high-value datasets by leveraging the NFDI infrastructure and adhering to FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). Its mission is to ensure that Earth system data is open, standardized, and efficiently reusable, thereby supporting the EU's goals for high-value

¹⁷ <https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Gesetze/Technologie-Innovation/iwg.html>

¹⁸ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=CELEX%3A32003L0098>

¹⁹ <https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/dng/index.html#BJNR294200021BJNE00070000>

²⁰ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/DE/TXT/?uri=CELEX:02016R0679-20160504>

Figure 1: Connection between legal requirements for governmental data and responsible authorities

datasets and fostering innovation across science and society.

2.2 Governmental metadata host – aggregator

A **metadata aggregator** is a service provider that collects, harmonizes, manages, preserves, and redistributes metadata from multiple sources. Aggregators serve as organisational and technical intermediaries between data-providing institutions (data providers) and downstream systems such as portals or APIs.

Typical responsibilities of an aggregator include:

- Harvesting metadata from various source systems on a regular basis,
- Transforming and standardizing metadata according to overarching frameworks (e.g., DCAT-AP),
- Managing persistent access points, interfaces, and data quality assurance mechanisms,
- Forwarding harmonized metadata to central or supranational data portals

A prominent example is **GovData**²¹, which harvests metadata from sources such as **GDI-DE**²² (Germany's Spatial Data Infrastructure) and **Destatis**²³ (the Federal Statistical Office). GDI-DE itself acts as an aggregator by collecting metadata from institutions such as the **German Weather Service (DWD)**, the **Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR)**, and **federal state-level geodata infrastructures**.

A **metadata host** is a service provider responsible for storing digital objects and their associated metadata. The hosting function includes:

- Capturing and maintaining metadata records,
- Presenting datasets and metadata through user-facing interfaces (e.g., web portals, map viewers),
- Providing machine-readable access via standardized APIs and protocols (e.g., CSW, WFS, SPARQL endpoints).

In addition to infrastructure, hosts often provide tools for metadata creation, validation, and version management, thereby supporting long-term usability and compliance with metadata standards.

The integration of aggregation and hosting capabilities within a single entity can be highly beneficial for:

- Ensuring consistent data quality through harmonized metadata handling,
- Providing stable and reliable access paths to metadata and datasets,
- Simplifying communication channels with both data providers and downstream consumers (e.g., research platforms or public data portals).

For example, **GDI-DE** acts as both a metadata host and aggregator for numerous federal agencies, whereas **GovData** mainly focuses on centralized aggregation and metadata distribution. Similarly, **umwelt.info** operates as a thematic host and aggregator within the environmental data sector. See the overview in Tab. 1.

²¹ <https://www.govdata.de>

²² <https://www.gdi-de.org>

²³ https://www.destatis.de/EN/Home/_node.html

Table 1: Overview to focused Aggregators, Metadata providers (governmental au Interfaces/ tandards for governmental data in Germany

Aggregator	Metadata Providers	Interface/Standard
GDI-DE	DWD, BGR, BKG, federal state infrastructures	INSPIRE-compliant CSW, ATOM Feed
GovData	GDI-DE, Destatis, etc.	DCAT-AP-DE (JSON / RDF)
umwelt.info	Authorities (federal, state, local) like BfG, BAW, BGR, GdWS, BSH, DESTATIS etc.	Several kinds of interfaces, a lot of sources INSPIRE-

Whether an aggregator, especially the GDI-DE, accepts and integrates metadata from a given source depends on several key criteria (*please note*, that none of these criteria is obligatory to be scraped or harvested by umwelt.info):

- **Standard Compliance:** Metadata must conform to established schemas such as [DCAT-AP-DE](#) or the [INSPIRE Metadata Regulation](#).
- **Machine-Readable Access:** Metadata must be available through open and standardized interfaces (e.g., CSW, SPARQL, REST APIs, ATOM feeds).
- **Persistence and Availability:** The metadata service must be consistently available, version-controlled, and technically reliable.
- **Licensing and Openness:** Metadata must include clear licensing terms (e.g., Data License Germany) that permit reuse in open data contexts.
- **Relevance and Currency:** The harvested metadata should be updated regularly and refer to publicly accessible, relevant datasets.

A sustainable and scalable research data infrastructure relies on **well-structured hosting and aggregation services**. Only through professional metadata management can governmental data become truly **FAIR** for the ESS community and the public alike.

Building on the overview of data aggregators presented in this chapter, the following subsections provide a closer look at key infrastructures—GDI-DE, GovData, and umwelt.info—as well as the NFDI4Earth initiative. These platforms illustrate how metadata aggregation and discoverability are implemented in practice.

Please note, that in the **HVD infrastructure**²⁴, there is no keyword “HVD” itself. Instead, **thematic designations** (e.g., “Meteorology”) are used as **keywords from a controlled vocabulary**, including the specification of the respective **thesaurus**. The challenges and opportunities outlined below serve to raise awareness within the research community, helping researchers understand why certain data may not yet be discoverable and how these insights can inform their own work on data and metadata. Researchers are invited to actively

²⁴ https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/hvd/annotation_in_geometadata

contribute to the further development of this report and to provide feedback via the **User Support Network²⁵ of NFDI4Earth**.

2.2.1 GDI-DE

The Geodateninfrastruktur Deutschland (GDI-DE) is a joint initiative of the Federal Government, the 16 federal states and municipal associations to make their spatial data interoperable and easily accessible online. It implements the EU INSPIRE Directive (2007/2/EC)²⁶ by providing central technical components—Geoportal.de²⁷, Geodatenkatalog.de²⁸, Registry²⁹, Testsuite³⁰ and Monitor³¹—that allow users to search, view, download and interlink geospatial datasets from all administrative levels.

GDI-DE's mission is to support science, administration, economy and the public by ensuring that distributed geodata (topographic, thematic, environmental, cadastral) conform to open OGC/ISO standards and FAIR principles. It thereby fosters cross-border and cross-sectoral collaboration in policy-making, research and applications.³²

The Coordination Office (Koordinierungsstelle) GDI-DE at the Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG) in Frankfurt am Main acts as Germany's National INSPIRE Point of Contact. It:

- Advises the Steering Committee (Lenkungsgrremium GDI-DE) on INSPIRE implementation³³
- Represents Germany in EU INSPIRE Working Groups and liaises with the European Commission
- Develops GDI-DE concepts, guidelines and best practices for metadata, services and data harmonisation.

2.2.1.1 GDI-DE monitoring metrics

²⁵ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>

²⁶ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2007/2/2024-11-26/eng>

²⁷ <https://geoportal.de>

²⁸ <https://geodatenkatalog.de/gdi-de/srv/ger/catalog.search#/home>

²⁹ <https://registry.gdi-de.org>

³⁰ <https://www.gdi-de.org/en/SDI/components/GDI-DE%20Testsuite>

³¹ <https://www.gdi-de.org/en/SDI/components/GDI-DE%20Monitor>

³² <https://www.gdi-de.org/>

³³ <https://ggim.un.org/UN-IGIF/documents/Aktionsplan-IGIF-german.pdf>

The GDI-DE Monitor is the national quality-assurance tool for checking availability and conformance of all metadata in the GDI-DE. As of the latest harvesting cycle (28.08.2025):

- 747 295 metadata records have been harvested into the Monitor
- 349 503 of these records are identified as INSPIRE-relevant (“inspireidentifiziert”), yielding a MDi1.1³⁴ (The number of spatial data sets for which metadata exist) conformance rate of 72 %
- 3176 datasets carry the HVD keyword, of which 54 originate from BGR and 3 from DWD
 - Those numbers are extracted directly via the monitoring tool and are not available for outside access. Questions regarding more precise queries and exact numbers should be directed to: support@gdi-de.org

2.2.1.2 GDI-DE operational observations and challenges

Based on the current state of the Monitor and HVD-tagging workflow, the following issues have been identified:

- **Inconsistent HVD thesaurus naming:** The HVD keyword is case-sensitive and not applied uniformly, making consolidation across records difficult
- **Downstream catalogs opaque:** Harvesting via Geodatenkatalog.de does not transparently identify secondary catalogs, hindering traceability of metadata origins
- **Outdated Monitor structure:** The existing Monitor UI and data model are antiquated; a redesign focused on metadata quality metrics is already underway
- **Mixed provider catalogs:** Multiple data-providing authorities (federal and Länder) share catalogs; since the “Bund” flag is assigned at catalog level, identifying the true origin of each dataset later is non-trivial
- **CSW performance limitations:** Current CSW queries are slow and were not designed for large-scale HVD searches
- **No CSW HVD thesaurus:** There is no dedicated HVD thesaurus for CSW, so HVD identification falls back on “any text” searches, resulting in imprecise tagging

Compiling these issues and challenges provides value to the research community: it raises awareness among researchers, helping to explain why certain data may not yet be discoverable. Additionally, these points can inform researchers’ own work on data and metadata. If further challenges are identified, they should be added to the list and communicated to the GDI-DE Monitor. In this way, the exercise also provides added value for GDI-DE.

³⁴ https://wiki.gdi-de.org/download/attachments/1334739009/DOC6_MIG10_IndicatorsGuide_v2019-07-19.pdf?api=v2

2.2.2 GovData

GovData³⁵ is the official open data portal of the German federal government. It serves as a central metadata aggregator and publication platform for administrative datasets originating from various levels of government—federal, state, and municipal. As a metadata hub, GovData enables structured, standardized, and FAIR-aligned access to public data, supporting scientific, administrative, and civic reuse. It relies primarily on the **DCAT-AP-DE**³⁶ metadata standard and provides interfaces for both manual access (via its web portal) and machine-readable harvesting³⁷ (via RDF, TURTLE and JSON-LD APIs).

Several federal institutions provide metadata to GovData that is relevant to the ESS domain. These include:

- **Federal Statistical Office (Destatis)** – Socio-environmental indicators, land use, demography,
- **Federal Environment Agency (UBA)** – Environmental monitoring data, air quality, water quality,
- **Federal Institute for Geosciences and Natural Resources (BGR)** – Geology, mineral resources, soil data,
- **German Meteorological Service (DWD)** – Climate and weather data,
- **Federal Maritime and Hydrographic Agency (BSH)** – Marine and coastal data,
- **Federal Agency for Cartography and Geodesy (BKG)** – Base geospatial datasets, topography, reference systems.

These institutions typically expose their metadata through INSPIRE-compliant or DCAT-based catalogs, which are harvested by GovData on a regular basis.

GovData plays a central role in the implementation of the European High-Value Dataset (EU-HVD) regulation. As Germany's official HVD focal point, GovData is tasked with publishing metadata for all federally maintained datasets falling under the six HVD categories (see HVD).

In addition to federal institutions, **state and municipal authorities** also contribute metadata to GovData. Examples include:

- **Open.NRW** (North Rhine-Westphalia),
- **OpenData.Berlin**,

³⁵ <https://www.govdata.de>

³⁶ <https://www.dcat-ap.de>

³⁷ <https://www.govdata.de/suche/daten/govdata-metadatenkatalog>

- and other regional platforms that syndicate their metadata through DCAT-AP-DE catalogs.

These non-federal contributors play a crucial role in publishing spatial and administrative datasets, often complementary to those of federal agencies. However, their metadata often lacks consistent HVD or thematic annotations relevant to ESS, limiting semantic discoverability.

2.2.2.1 GovData monitoring metrics

The following results are based on our own survey conducted on the GovData portal. For this purpose, the portal's search function and the keyword *HVD* were used. This approach relates solely to the search and retrieval process within the portal and does not imply that *HVD* is used as a keyword in the underlying metadata.

As of August 13, 2025, the platform lists:

- 6,295 HVD-designated metadata records,
- of which 5,206 are INSPIRE-identified datasets (“inspireidentifiziert”),
- and 642 datasets are tagged with the keyword “HVD”.

45 HVD datasets come directly from the BGR, 9 from the BKG and 34 from DWD.

HVD metadata is not consistently annotated with thematic keywords from controlled vocabularies, which restricts discoverability through keyword-based filtering. This inconsistency points to the need for improved metadata annotation practices, particularly with respect to the application of controlled vocabularies and the classification of datasets as HVD. Nonetheless, GovData has begun aligning its metadata practices with EU implementation guidelines, including the systematic use of controlled vocabularies and semantic tagging.

Germany's reporting on high-value datasets under Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2023/138³⁸ may reference its national open data catalogue (GovData) for metadata, API and licence links (Art. 5(3)(a)–(c)). The EU framework monitors Member State compliance for the following points:

- completeness and timeliness of HVD publication,
- interface availability,
- and accessibility of metadata and underlying datasets.

2.2.2.2 GovData operational observations and challenges

³⁸ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg_impl/2023/138/oj/eng

While GovData provides essential infrastructure for metadata aggregation, several challenges have been observed. In particular, the incomplete mapping of ISO 19139 to DCAT-AP-DE leads to a loss of metadata at the aggregator site:

- **Inconsistent use of the “HVD” keyword** across datasets, making search and filtering unreliable,
- **Incomplete thesaurus integration**, limiting semantic interoperability and keyword harmonisation across data providers,
- **Redundant metadata entries** or catalog overlaps due to repeated harvesting from both federal and regional catalogs (e.g., the same dataset listed by both BKG and GDI-DE),
- **Lack of linkage** between metadata records and authoritative vocabularies (e.g., GEMET, INSPIRE themes),
- **Variation in metadata quality**, especially in descriptive fields such as abstract, temporal coverage, and licensing,
- **Sparse metadata for APIs or real-time data feeds**, which are increasingly important for research in Earth System Sciences.

GovData fulfills a vital role as Germany’s central metadata aggregator, especially in the context of EU-HVD implementation. While its coverage and technical infrastructure are substantial, **metadata quality assurance, keyword governance, and semantic annotation practices** remain areas for improvement. Continued alignment with the FAIR principles and EU metadata guidelines will be key to increasing the value of GovData for scientific users, particularly in the Earth System Sciences.

2.2.3 UBA umwelt.info

umwelt.info³⁹ is a search engine developed by the German Umweltbundesamt (Federal Environment Agency, UBA) as a central access point to publicly available environmental and nature conservation data across Germany. It aims to make environmental information—such as maps, measurements, research findings, educational materials, and funding program descriptions—findable and comparable. The search results are evaluated based on the fulfillment of the FAIR criteria. The portal umwelt.info is hosted by the UBA (National Center for Environmental and Nature Conservation Information).

The web portal complements the offerings of **GDI-DE** and **GovData** with a thematic, user-oriented access point that focuses on environmental topics and makes searching easier for both experts and non-experts. For ESS researchers, umwelt.info provides an intuitive, central

³⁹ <https://umwelt.info>

entry point to locate relevant environmental datasets across various institutions—ranging from federal agencies to civil society. The portal’s intelligent search functionality, combined with editorial content and clearly displayed metadata, enhances data discovery and lowers access barriers.

umwelt.info collects metadata and references to datasets. Harvesting covers a broad range of providers—including federal agencies, research institutions, regional authorities, NGOs, and even private individuals or organizations. The engine harvests metadata via technical interfaces—such as APIs—where available, and employs web harvesting (crawling) and scraping to gather metadata from sources that lack machine-readable interfaces⁴⁰. The internal metadata model is influenced by DCAT-AP.de but remains flexible enough to accommodate diverse, non-standard data sources.

The portal does not store full datasets, but integrates metadata—like titles, descriptions, licenses, spatial and temporal extent, source links, and resource links to datasets if openly accessible—into its search index. If metadata are missing or unstructured, umwelt.info creates structured metadata (e.g., via scraping) to ensure consistency and discoverability.

2.2.3.1 UBA monitoring metrics

There is no publicly displayed metric on umwelt.info about how many HVDs are listed. While the portal may indeed capture metadata from HVD sources, the number of HVDs, completeness, or timeliness is not reported in its public interface or documentation.

2.2.3.2 UBA operational Observations and opportunities

While the portal’s flexible metadata (and data) search capabilities offer clear advantages, they also pose several challenges:

- **Heterogeneity of data sources:** Because umwelt.info harvests from very diverse systems, **metadata quality and format vary widely**— making stringent filtering necessary before applying the index for individual use cases.
- **Metadata standardization limits:** umwelt.info does not impose a strict metadata standard but uses an adaptive internal schema. This ensures wide coverage but can impact consistency⁴¹. Therefore umwelt.info offer a publicly accessible API based on CKAN-standard.
- **Completeness vs. feasibility:** Since not all data providers offer APIs or structured metadata, some sources must be scraped—raising concerns about completeness,

⁴⁰ <https://umwelt.info/de/artikel/ueber-den-metadatenexport>

⁴¹ <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/umweltinfo-faq>

freshness, and data integrity. At the same time, scraping enables the capture of additional, even unstructured, content, but this approach introduces specific challenges that need to be carefully addressed and resolved.

- **Scaling editorial support:** Presenting thematic, curated search results and editorial context (articles, infographics) requires ongoing coordination and resource allocation⁴². Currently, this is implemented through dedicated editorial workflows at [umwelt.info](https://www.umwelt.info), where experts curate and contextualise content for specific environmental and thematic domains.
- **Data provider engagement:** Encouraging agencies and institutions to expose structured metadata (e.g., via DCAT or APIs) remains crucial and challenging. The portal is open to advising organizations on best practices.

In the governmental domain, there are additional portals—beyond those previously mentioned—that collect structured metadata to varying degrees. However, as far as we can determine, all of this metadata is harvested by one of the aggregators we have already discussed.

2.3 GDI-DE Profile convention for metadata of High-Value Datasets

To ensure consistent identification, discovery, and harvesting of HVD, the GDI-DE has issued a binding profile convention for ISO 19115/19139 metadata applicable to all datasets falling under the scope of the DVO-HVD. This requirement supplements the general metadata conventions described in Chapter 6 of GDI-DE “Konventionen zu Metadaten”⁴³, which govern all Open Data transfers to the national portal GovData.

A dataset is recognised as HVD within the GDI-DE ecosystem only if its metadata explicitly carries the HVD tag as prescribed by the profile convention. Such tagging ensures that the dataset is ingested into GovData and is counted toward Germany’s national DVO-HVD reporting obligations.

Within each `gmd:descriptiveKeywords` element, one of the six EU HVD category Uniform Resource Identifiers (URIs) must be embedded as a `gmx:Anchor` value, for example:

In each `gmd:descriptiveKeywords` section, one of the six EU HVD-category URIs must be inserted as a `gmx:Anchor`:

⁴² <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/umweltinfo-start-tab>

⁴³ https://www.gdi-de.org/download/AK_Metadaten_Konventionen_zu_Metadaten.pdf

Figure 2: Workflow for High-Value Dataset metadata within the GDI-DE framework.

HVD Category (German categories)	URI
Geospatial (Georaum)	<http://data.europa.eu/bna/c_ac64a52d>
Earth Observation and Environment (Erdbbeobachtung und Umwelt)	<http://data.europa.eu/bna/c_dd313021>
Meteorology (Meteorologie)	<http://data.europa.eu/bna/c_164e0bf5>
Statistics (Statistik)	<http://data.europa.eu/bna/c_e1da4e07>
Business and Ownership Information (Unternehmen und Eigentümerschaft von Unternehmen)	<http://data.europa.eu/bna/c_a9135398>
Mobility (Mobilität)	<http://data.europa.eu/bna/c_b79e35eb>

The list provided by the Publications Office of the EU itself is referenced as the associated source in the `thesaurusName` element as follows:

- `title` element: `gmx:Anchor` pointing to “<http://data.europa.eu/bna/asd487ae75>”
- `date` element: “2023-09-27” with `dateType="publication"`

As an interim compatibility measure, metadata records may alternatively include the German category name as free text while citing HVD categories in the `gmd:thesaurusName` element.

The associated source is specified in the `thesaurusName` element as follows:

- `title` element: “High-value dataset categories”
- `date` element: “2023-09-27”
- `dateType` element: “publication”

However, this approach is less robust for automated harvesting and is therefore discouraged in favour of the URI-based method.

Fig. 2 summarizes the path from the original data provider through the GDI-DE metadata catalogue to the GovData national portal and, ultimately, to DVO-HVD reporting. HVD tagging according to the GDI-DE profile convention is applied at the metadata ingestion stage.

2.3.1 Observed shortcomings and next steps

- National scope only⁴⁴ – The DVO-HVD requires coverage at Member State level; transboundary datasets of relevance to ESS are currently excluded.
- Metadata-only limitation⁴⁵ – HVD tagging addresses discoverability but does not guarantee underlying data quality, completeness, or interoperability.
- Pipeline reliability issues⁴⁶ – Variations in thesaurus naming (including case sensitivity) and the absence of a dedicated HVD thesaurus in the CSW endpoint reduce harvesting consistency.

These results are expected to be incorporated into the planned redesign of the GDI-DE monitor and the HVD processing pipeline. The objective is to implement more rigorous metadata quality controls, harmonised thesaurus handling, and end-to-end traceability from the original data provider to the national GovData reporting framework.

3 Method for increasing gov-data

Ensuring that gov-data relevant to ESS is **findable, accessible, and usable** requires more than simply publishing metadata. It depends on a coordinated strategy for searching, aggregating, and validating metadata across multiple portals, with consistent use of standards and identifiers. In addition, robust quality controls for (meta)data and semantic search options play a key role in improving the findability and reuse of government data in research.

This chapter presents a workflow for improving gov-data visibility through the *NFDI4Earth OneStop4All*⁴⁷ (OneStop4All) portal as the primary discovery interface for scientists with the *NFDI4Earth KnowledgeHub*⁴⁸ serving as its metadata backend. HVD are used as a worked example, both because of their legal relevance under *DVO-HVD* and because they present an excellent test case for end-to-end data pipeline quality. For OneStop4All to function as a comprehensive discovery service, it must integrate gov-data from national metadata providers (e.g., GDI-DE, GovData). Within this framework, HVD can be flagged or prioritized in the KnowledgeHub to highlight their importance for ESS research.

⁴⁴ https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/hvd/Reporting_guidelines_for_HVDs

⁴⁵ https://dataeuropa.gitlab.io/data-provider-manual/hvd/Reporting_guidelines_for_HVDs

⁴⁶ <https://www.loc.gov/catworkshop/lcsh/PDF%20scripts/1-2-WhyCV.pdf>

⁴⁷ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de>

⁴⁸ <https://knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de>

3.1 Search definition

The process begins with the definition of the search scope. This includes:

- **Dataset scope** – e.g., all HVD categories relevant to ESS:
 - Geospatial (land use, administrative boundaries)
 - Earth Observation & Environment (remote sensing products, habitat maps)
 - Meteorological (weather station data, climate series)
- **Target authorities** – e.g.,
 - Deutscher Wetterdienst (DWD) for meteorological HVD,
 - Bundesanstalt für Geowissenschaften und Rohstoffe (BGR) for geological HVD.
- **Additional filters** – e.g., “High-Value Dataset” tagging, spatial coverage (national), temporal coverage (past 30 years), formats (NetCDF, CSV, GeoPackage), licences (Open Data). In order to make search definitions more effective, it is essential to supplement them with **semantic search options** (e.g., synonyms, ontologies, controlled vocabularies), as these compensate for differences in terminology between portals and authorities.

Example: Define a search for Meteorological HVD provided by DWD, with the keywords “climate time series” and “station observations”, restricted to datasets covering Germany in machine-readable form.

3.2 Data availability search

The defined search is executed in parallel across three primary platforms:

1. **GDI-DE** (national INSPIRE-based spatial data catalogue),
2. **GovData** (German national open data portal), and
3. **OneStop4All** (NFDI4Earth).

For each platform, the number of matching datasets is recorded. This produces a 3×2 result matrix for the example of two authorities (three platforms \times two counts: HVD-tagged matches for DWD and BGR).

Example: In addition to GDI-DE (Chapter 2.2.1 produces a 3×2 result matrix for the example of two authorities (three platforms \times two counts: HVD-tagged matches for DWD and BGR).

Example: In addition to GDI-DE (Chapter 2.2.1) and GovData (Chapter 2.2.2), a targeted search was conducted in the KnowledgeHub via SPARQL query⁴⁹.

A manual search was also performed via the web portal OneStop4All. Here, results vary significantly depending on the applied keyword. The example of HVD data yields the results shown in {Tab. 3}.

Table 3: Comparison of HVD dataset availability across infrastructures

Platform / Source	Total HVD datasets	DWD	BGR
GDI-DE Monitor	3176	3	54
GovData	6295	34	45
KnowledgeHub: keyword "HVD"	602		
KnowledgeHub: keyword "hvd"	1		
OneStop4All: keyword "HVD"	1144	4	0
OneStop4All: keyword "High-value data"	460	0	20

The search is a snapshot, so you can't expect everything to match up perfectly. Still, there are some clear differences: The numbers vary widely across platforms. OneStop4All shows strong **keyword dependency**, with DWD and BGR datasets only discoverable under different terms. These inconsistencies confirm that **metadata harmonisation and thesaurus alignment** are necessary to improve visibility and ensure reliable harvesting into OneStop4All. The highly keyword-dependent hits in OneStop4All underscore the need for **thesaurus-based and semantic search**, which standardizes different spellings and synonyms.

3.3 Coverage comparison

The counts are compared to detect coverage gaps:

- Are all HVD-tagged datasets present in OneStop4All?
- Do any exist in GDI-DE or GovData but are missing from OneStop4All?
- Are some HVD datasets missing an HVD tag in metadata?

Such deviations can be reduced through **systematic quality controls** (e.g., validation of HVD tags, automated checks for gaps).

Example analysis: The DWD climate series appear in GDI-DE and GovData, but two datasets are missing in OneStop4All due to absent HVD tags in the harvested metadata. One additional dataset is missing entirely because it is only published on the DWD website without portal integration.

⁴⁹ <https://sparql.knowledgehub.nfdi4earth.de/> (follow link for full query)

3.4 Direct action and feedback channels

When gaps are detected, the following actions are initiated:

- **Portal-level contact** – Use official feedback channels of GDI-DE and GovData to report missing records.
- **Authority-level contact** – Directly approach the responsible agency (e.g., DWD, BGR) to address metadata publication or tagging issues.
- **NFDI4Earth support structures** – Utilise the *Interest Group Metadata* and the NFDI4Earth Helpdesk to coordinate follow-up, track issues, and propose standardisation improvements.

Example action: For the missing DWD datasets, OneStop4All project staff submit an issue to the IG Metadata mailing list, tagging it as “HVD gap – meteorology”. The DWD data officer is contacted via GDI-DE feedback form to update metadata records with the proper HVD URI.

3.5 Identification of weak points and solution pathways

The process (see Fig. 3) not only identifies missing datasets but also highlights systemic weaknesses such as:

- Metadata inconsistencies (e.g., non-standard HVD category naming),
- Gaps in harvesting pipelines from source catalogues to OneStop4All,
- Lack of prioritisation or highlighting for HVD in search interfaces.

These findings feed into a *solution blueprint* (Anders et al., 2024⁵⁰) to propose technical fixes such as:

- Establishment of automated quality control for (meta)data,
- Greater harmonisation of metadata with ontologies and controlled vocabularies,
- Integration of semantic search mechanisms into OneStop4All to take synonyms and multilingualism into account,
- Enforcing URI-based HVD tagging in metadata,
- Expanding KnowledgeHub harvesting endpoints,
- Implementing an “HVD priority” search filter in OneStop4All.

⁵⁰ Anders, I., Kaspar, F., Kratzenstein, F., Schupfner, M., & Thiemann, H. (2024). Standardisation and making public authority data available for research. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10948876>

Figure 3: Workflow for identifying and resolving gaps in the visibility of governmental data.

4 Recommendations

Building on the findings from Chapters 2 and 3 and informed by stakeholder workshops, this chapter summarises actionable recommendations to improve the discoverability, accessibility, and usability of governmental data (gov-data) for Earth System Science (ESS). The recommendations draw on lessons learnt from:

- **NFDI4Earth HVD Workshop** (Hamburg, November 2024), and
- **GDI-DE Workshop “High-Value Datasets from a User Perspective”** (March 2025).

The measures outlined here address technical, organisational, and collaborative dimensions of the HVD pipeline and can also be applied to gov-data more broadly.

4.1 Strengthening feedback channels

Observation:

Both workshops highlighted the absence of a formalised feedback mechanism for scientists to report missing datasets, metadata issues, or usability problems back to governmental authorities and portal operators.

Recommendations:

- **Establish a persistent feedback channel** – potentially via the *User Support Network (USN)* of NFDI4Earth – to collect, triage, and forward issues to data providers.
- **Leverage existing structures** – integrate with GDI-DE’s and GovData’s support forms, while maintaining a central NFDI4Earth tracking system.

- **Pre-publication feedback loop** – before releasing new HVD datasets, run a quick expert review (scientists) to verify metadata completeness, file usability, and documentation quality.
- To further ensure data quality, **automated checks for metadata completeness and HVD tag consistency** should complement the expert pre-publication review.

4.2 Improving data preparation and documentation

Observation:

Several datasets suffer from insufficient guidance on access, format, and structure. Examples from the workshops include:

- Lack of code snippets or download instructions.
- No documentation for file contents (e.g. time ranges, variable lists).
- Ambiguous or proprietary formats without explanation (e.g. .cap XML format).
- Deviations from standard formats not documented (e.g. SYNOP data exceptions).

Recommendations:

- **Provide minimal technical onboarding** for each dataset:
 - Short description of contents.
 - Information on spatial/temporal coverage.
 - Supported formats and conversion hints (e.g. Shapefile to GeoPackage).
 - Sample code (Python, R) for download and parsing.
- **Standardise file structures** where possible; where not possible, provide explicit exceptions documentation.
- **Ensure primary data access** for datasets that are currently only available in derived form (e.g. D-AERO).
- Additionally, consistent use of **controlled vocabularies and clear thesaurus references** will improve interoperability and enable semantic search across platforms.

4.3 Metadata quality for scientific use

Observation:

Scientific workflows require richer metadata than is sometimes provided under minimal Open Data obligations. The *White Paper: Recommendations for Earth System Sciences Metadata Provision* offers a useful reference, which could be aligned with gov-data conventions and HVD metadata profiles.

Recommendations:

- **Adopt ESS-specific metadata extensions** for HVD in addition to mandatory DCAT/ISO elements (e.g., variable list, processing history, uncertainty estimates).
- **Automated quality control procedures** should be established to validate metadata formats, completeness, and adherence to controlled vocabularies.
- **Harmonise tagging practices** for HVD categories (URI-based, case-consistent).
- **Semantic search mechanisms**, including synonym resolution and multilingual support, should be integrated to enhance discoverability for diverse scientific workflows.
- **Promote registration of authorities in re3data**, ensuring institutional persistence and visibility in the research data ecosystem.

4.4 Enhancing cross-sector collaboration

Observation:

Sustainable improvement of HVD quality and usability requires ongoing interaction between data providers and the scientific community.

Recommendations:

- **Create regular exchange formats** – e.g., thematic workshops, joint metadata hackathons, or an online forum moderated by NFDI4Earth.
- **Document and share use cases** where scientist–authority collaboration improved data quality, serving as blueprints for other domains.
- **Highlight mutual benefits** – better usability increases scientific uptake, while positive exposure strengthens the mandate for open data provision.
- **Collaboration** should also support the **continuous monitoring and versioning of harvesting pipelines** between source portals (GDI-DE, GovData) and the OneStop4All / KnowledgeHub to ensure data consistency and reliability over time.

4.5 Contact points to science

Observation:

Authorities often lack established communication channels to the research community, leading to one-way data publication without iterative improvement.

Recommendations:

- **Map existing contact networks** – identify existing liaison roles, committees, or domain-specific working groups that could bridge science–authority communication.
- **Integrate these channels into NFDI4Earth** – ensuring they are discoverable via the OneStop4All KnowledgeHub.
- **Develop a rapid-response mechanism** – enabling timely feedback and resolution without multi-month delays.

These measures collectively address the key questions outlined at the beginning of this report: enabling authorities to publish and annotate data effectively, improving scientists' ability to find and access data, and ensuring a sustainable, high-quality data pipeline.

Overall priority actions:

1. Set up a coordinated feedback and tracking mechanism via NFDI4Earth.
2. Enrich HVD metadata and documentation for scientific workflows.
3. Establish sustainable collaboration formats between authorities and scientists.
4. Ensure consistent metadata tagging and authority registration in research data registries.

Table 4: Compilation of recommendations with responsibilities, prioritization, and expected impact

Re commendation	Respons ible	Priority	Expected Impact
Establish persistent feedback channel (via NFDI4Earth USN)	NFDI4Earth, GDI-DE, GovData	High	Continuous improvement of data quality and completeness through direct issue reporting.
Implement p re-publication feedback loop for HVD	Data-providing authorities, NFDI4Earth experts	Medium	Early correction of meta data/usability issues before public release.
Provide minimal technical onboarding (docs + code snippets) for each dataset	Data providers (e.g., DWD, BGR)	High	Reduced entry barriers for ESS scientists, faster dataset integration in workflows.
Standardise file structures or document deviations	Data providers	Medium	Increased in teroperability and reduced processing time for end users.
Ensure primary data access where only derived data is provided	Data providers	High	Enables r eproducibility and advanced scientific analyses.

Re commendation	Respons ible	Priority	Expected Impact
Adopt ESS-specific metadata extensions for HVD	Data providers, NFDI4Earth IG Metadata	Medium	Improved scientific relevance and discoverability of datasets.
Harmonise tagging practices for HVD categories	Data providers, metadata catalog operators	Medium	Consistent search results and reduced false negatives in dataset discovery.
Register authorities in re3data	Data providers, institutional data managers	Low	Increased international visibility and integration in research data infrastructures.
Create regular exchange formats (forums, workshops, hackathons)	NFDI4Earth, authorities, ESS community	Medium	Strengthened trust and shared understanding between data providers and scientists.
Map and integrate existing science contact networks	NFDI4Earth, authorities	High	Direct and efficient communication between stakeholders, enabling rapid feedback cycles.
Develop a rapid-response mechanism for feedback resolution	Authorities, NFDI4Earth USN	High	Timely corrections and improvements without long delays, ensuring up-to-date data availability.

5 Outlook

The present report constitutes an initial step toward enhancing the discoverability and usability of governmental data (gov-data) for the Earth System Science (ESS) community. A follow-up version — planned as **Deliverable D2.3.2** — will incorporate direct feedback from ESS researchers to refine both the methodological approach and the technical recommendations.

To ensure that the updated report reflects the practical needs of its users, feedback channels will be actively promoted and maintained. Options include:

- **User Support Network (USN)**⁵¹ and its ticketing system, enabling structured and trackable issue reporting.
- **Direct author contact** for case-specific inputs.

The choice of feedback mechanism will depend on the required immediacy, the complexity of the feedback, and the need for follow-up discussions. Engagement will be further supported by targeted calls for contributions via ESS mailing lists, NFDI4Earth communication channels, and relevant community forums.

⁵¹ <https://onestop4all.nfdi4earth.de/>

The continued development of workflows and conventions for metadata and data publication will be aligned with ongoing work in **standardization bodies (e.g., DIN)** and relevant European and international initiatives. This will ensure that national practices remain interoperable with broader frameworks and benefit from community-driven best practices.

Future efforts must not focus solely on the discovery of datasets, but also on their transformation into value-added products and services:

1. **From Data □ to Data Products** – ensuring validation, standardization, and rich metadata to guarantee scientific reusability.
2. **From Data Products □ to Data Services** – offering static and dynamic portals or APIs for visualization, analysis, editing, downloading, and generating actionable insights.

This progression will support a fully FAIR-aligned ecosystem, where datasets are not only findable but also directly usable in applied and research contexts.

The next phase of work will be guided by four interlinked goals:

1. **Finding the Data** – integrating services and metadata search engines for comprehensive discovery across domains and infrastructures.
2. **Using the Data** – providing clear access and enabling effective FAIR-compliant utilization.
3. **Interoperable Data** – ensuring compatibility across disciplines, applications, and regions.
4. **Reusable Data** – facilitating adaptation and application of datasets for new use cases.

Through this framework, the future work will progressively close existing gaps, improve collaboration between public authorities and ESS scientists, and strengthen the overall infrastructure for open and interoperable gov-data.

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